

Relative Effectiveness of Cognitive Restructuring and Contingency Contracting Techniques on Bullying Behaviour Among Secondary School Students in Imo State

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Abstract

This study investigated the relative effectiveness of cognitive restructuring and contingency contracting techniques on bullying behaviour among secondary school students in Imo-state. One research question guided the study and one hypothesis was tested at 0.5 level of significance. The research design was quasi experimental research design. The population for the study was a total of 265 senior secondary students identified with bullying behaviour constituted the population of the study. Purposive sampling technique was employed to select 94 secondary students used as the sample for the study. The instrument for data collection was bullying behaviour identification inventory (BBII). Statistical mean and ANCOVA were used in answering the research questions and hypotheses respectively. Results obtained from the study indicated that contingency contracting was slightly more effective than cognitive restructuring technique in the treatment of bullying behaviour, but the difference in the effectiveness of the two techniques on bullying behaviours among secondary school students is not significant. Based on the findings, the researchers recommended that both contingency contracting and cognitive restructuring techniques should be adopted by school counsellors and other allied professionals as a means of reducing bullying behaviour in our school setting. Also, the school counsellors should be trained on the effective use of skills and techniques to improve problem solving abilities.

Key words: *Effectiveness, Cognitive restructuring, Contingency contracting, Techniques, Bullying behaviour, Students*

Introduction

Learning environment at home or school should provide a sense of security to every child. However, experience from daily observation has shown that such expected security is not being realized today owing to occurrence of many unwanted behaviour such as use of dangerous weapons, fighting, aggressiveness and bullying. These bullying behaviours are exhibited by some children, especially those in the secondary schools. Over the years, there has been increasing incidence of such oppressive behaviour among secondary school adolescents in Nigeria and the world over (Egbochukwu, 2007; Turkmen, Dokgoz & Vural, 2013). This trend is worrisome and unacceptable to every well-thinking person in every culture and has led to taking measures like flogging, kneeling down, standing up, giving of suspensions to bullies, expulsion, and other forms of corporal punishments to curb the occurrence of such maladaptive behaviours both at home and in the schools. Nevertheless, in spite of concerted efforts made by school officials, teachers, parents and students towards ensuring that schools are friendlier and safer places, anti-social behaviours such as threats, armed assaults, aggressiveness, explosive temper tantrum and other forms of bullying still persist.

Bullying behaviour according to Aluede and Fajoju (2011), is described as a form of aggression, a particular kind of violence exhibited in the course of social interaction by a more dominant individual (the bully) to a less dominant individual (the victim) with the intention to cause distress to the victim. Such bullying behaviour may include name calling, verbal or written abuse, exclusion from activities and social situations, physical abuse or coercion. It could equally include digital bullying which according to American Psychiatric Association (2010) involves using cell phones and computers to send menacing text messages or creating threatening and hate-filled web pages about a victim including personal information.

The existence of different forms of bullying in schools today affects lots of students and even becoming a bigger crisis with vicious consequences in recent times. For instance, children who are bullied can experience negative physical and mental health issues, they may experience depression and anxiety, may have increased feeling of sadness and loneliness with certain level of suicidal tendencies. They may also have changes in sleep and eating pattern as well as loss of interest in activities they used to enjoy. Therefore, bullying as noted by Thornberry (2010) is not just a child's play but a terrifying experience many school children face every day. To buttress this fact, bullying can be seen as the source of increased concern especially the use of violence or threatened violence against children at, or near school.

Hence, bullying in the context of this study is to be seen as repeated use of a written, verbal, electronic expression, any physical act or gesture or any of the above combination by a student or group of students (bullies) against another student (victim) with the intent to harass, ridicule, humiliate, intimidate, or harm the other targeted student. The above definition is encompassing and captures every aspect of unholy behaviour exhibited by bullies both at home, in and around school environment. This repeated act may cause physical or emotional harm or cause damage to the victim's property; it may create a hostile environment at school, infringe on their rights and substantially disrupt the education process and orderly operation of a school.

However, the most worrisome is the impact of bullying behaviour on the learning –teaching situation where bullies might out of constant thinking of the bully’s harassment develop attention deficit disorder. This disorder makes it difficult for students to be well adjusted to learn and on the other hand, teachers found themselves engaging in constant remedial teaching just to ensure they carry these students along. Again, students who are bullied according to Kline and Silver (2004) might externalize stress. By so doing, they externalize the anxiety and depression they are facing by projecting all of their problems onto others and blame everyone for the problem they are facing. The truth remains that a teacher that cares about her students may also be depressed too. When the above scenario becomes the issue, there will likely be disruption in the smooth running of operation in the teaching learning situation. This invariably affects everyone,

Bullying behaviour is not limited to a particular gender. Both males and females exhibit different levels and types of bullying behaviour. There are multiple theories that seek to explain findings that make males and females to have different aggressive behaviours. Givens (2009) for instance, in studying aggression and bullying behaviour, found out that adolescent females get involved more relational aggression (emotional) compared to adolescent males. Givens’ study corroborated that of Paus (2005) which suggested that males make more use of physical aggressive behaviours while females use verbal aggression than males.

Naturally, one would assume that male would be more prone to bullying than female adolescents, but from the foregoing, both males and females tend to exhibit different types and levels of bullying behaviour. Researches such as Asamu (2006) and Omoteso (2010) have also shown the variations in the prevalence of bullying among boys and girls. For instance, while Asamu found that 21% of the students studied in Ibadan who had bullied other students were male, Omoteso discovered that 48.8% male and 51.2% female were involved in bullying. Consequently, bullying behaviour either by male or female is a ‘red flag’ that a student has not learned to control his or her aggression. Students that bully need counselling to learn healthy ways to interact with people.

Reports in literature such as Espelage, Mebane and Swearer (2004), reveal that teachers have been trying to control this behaviour through the application of different types of punishment measures. The measures as noted by Eze (2009) include flogging, manual work, (of different types), kneeling down, writing imposition, standing up in the class and sending the individual out. These measures are today perceived as inappropriate as there is observable increase in the rate of the behaviour and the dimensions employed despite the effort in controlling its occurrence. The increase and dimensions involved and prevalence observed by earlier researchers almost certainly indicate that the measure adopted by schools (teachers) in fighting this canker worm seems ineffective or inadequate and may possibly be reinforcing the behaviour. Although, studies such as Adeusi, 2013; Eweniyi, Adeoye, Ayodele and Adebayo, (2013) have shown that application of counselling techniques could guide students through discovering that bullying is as a result of irrational or maladaptive thoughts, it still remains a source of worry and concern to students, parents, counsellors and society at large. Among the techniques and therapies whose efficacy had been tested, the researchers realised that the use of cognitive restructuring and contingency contracting techniques had been used to adequately address the

issue of truancy, lateness to school, constant fighting. The researchers also adopted the techniques to address the issue of bullying among secondary school in Imo-state, this necessitated this study. Bullying has been clearly identified as one of the early warning signs that students are potentially headed for violent and delinquent activities, social isolation or educational failure. Undoubtedly, bullying is related to delinquency, poor self concept, poor academic performance, suicidal ideations and attempts. Abstracting from this, it is also believed that such behavioural excesses and inappropriateness among students can be modified. Efforts at addressing the problem do not seem successful because of the reported increases rather than expected decreases. However, many researchers on behaviour modification have paid much attention to the use of cognitive restructuring for modifying undesirable behaviour among the students.

Cognitive restructuring is a technique in cognitive behavioural therapy developed by Aaron Beck in the 1960s and aims at replacing one's "faulty thinking" and irrational counterfactual beliefs with more accurate and beneficial ones. It is a psychotherapeutic process of learning to identify and dispute irrational or maladaptive thoughts. According to Oguzie, Ani, Obi and Onyegirim (2018), cognitive restructuring technique is a behaviour change technique that deals with the potential effect of clients' attribution on the change and maintenance of behaviour. This approach does not involve distorting reality in a positive direction or attempting to believe the unbelievable. Rather it uses reason and evidence to replace distorted thought patterns that are not useful. There are many methods used in cognitive restructuring, which usually involve identifying and labelling distorted thoughts. These methods according to Huppert (2009) include Socratic questioning, thought recording, identifying cognitive errors, examining the evidence (pro-con analysis or cost-benefit analysis), understanding idiosyncratic meaning/semantic techniques, reattribution, guided imagery and listing rational alternatives. Mills, Reiss and Beck (2008) opined that cognitive restructuring teaches one to stop trusting in one's automatic tendency and also to stop accepting the contents of one's thoughts as being an accurate assessment of reality, instead the goal is to start testing each thought that one have to assess its accuracy. Therefore, the bully can actually checkmate his thoughts especially when the urge to bully heightens.

Cognitive restructuring technique has recorded success in managing a range of behavioural problems as revealed by research findings (Malenka, Nestler & Hyman, 2009). Walsh (2013) for instance successfully used cognitive restructuring to treat depression caused by cyber bullying. Similarly, Anyamene, Nwokolo and Nwosu (2017) study of the effects of cognitive restructuring technique on lateness among secondary school students, revealed that cognitive restructuring technique is effective in modifying lateness behaviour. So, the technique has been employed in modifying some behaviours among secondary school adolescents with some measure of success. For example, while the study by Olufunmilola (2014), showed the efficacy of cognitive restructuring on bullying as a conduct disorder, Olatunbosun and Ugwu's (2016) study revealed that cognitive behaviour therapy had significant efficacy of reducing bullying on the experimental group of studies in carried out in Ikwerre, Rivers state. Thus, the technique, according to Lohmann (2014), is the most widely acclaimed, trusted and research supported treatment method for the treatment of conduct problems. This perhaps could be attributed to the

notion that Cognitive behaviour therapy teaches individuals to understand their thoughts and feelings better in relation to the situation. Furthermore, it teaches how their thoughts and feelings, as well as beliefs, influence their actions and ultimately their behaviour. In the context of this study, cognitive restructuring can be defined as a therapeutic tool used by the counsellor to ensure that the client maintains a sound reasoning and gives an objective interpretation of a case regardless of the cause of problematic circumstance in question.

Hence, in choosing between various behaviour management techniques, it is necessary to consider that even an evidence-based practice may not be effective if the counsellor or therapist lacks the skill or motivation to implement it with commitment. As Elswick and Casey (2011) note, counsellors are not only interested in an intervention's effectiveness, but are also concerned with the amount of time required to implement a given approach. They prefer easy-to- implement interventions, and one potentially easy-to-implement individualized behaviour management approach is a contingency contract. Contingency contracting in the educational setting includes the manipulation of antecedent and consequence variables to affect a student's patterns of behaviour. Contracting involves creating a written document between the teacher and the student that specifies a target behaviour, a set criterion for performance of the target behaviour, and the consequence available to the student upon meeting that criterion (Downey, 2007).

Moreover, contingency contracting is a technique in which an agreement is reached between the therapist and his client(s) with regard to the role each person is required to play to enable the client undergo behaviour change. According to Derenne and Flannery (2007), contingency management is the careful manipulation of antecedent and consequent events in the environment by one person or more in order to manage a target behaviour and achieve positive change in the desired direction. The choice of contingency contracting technique as Obi (2004) observed was motivated by its success in managing a range of behavioural problems. Contingency contracting has also been employed in modifying peer-bullying among primary school pupils in Edo state with some measure of success (Chima, 2006; Oliha & Audu, 2013). Thus, contingency contracting technique can compare favourably with other technique as behaviour change techniques. Contextually, contingency contracting can be defined as keeping a close monitoring on a client to detect exhibition of a good behaviour in other to give reward as soon as the behaviour occurs.

In addition, as an antecedent approach, counsellors could use a contract to identify a target behaviour, a specific consequence for emitting certain rates of the behaviour, and duration of the contract or number of behaviour occurrences needed to meet the agreed contingency, then consequences are delivered if the contract goal is met. The effects of Contingency contracting and Cognitive restructuring techniques on students' maladaptive behaviours meet the criteria of a positive behaviour change technique for students with bullying behaviour.

The efficacy of cognitive restructuring and contingency contracting techniques to shape or modify maladaptive behaviours in children is evident in a growing volume of behaviour studies (Adeusi, 2013; Modo, Akpabio & Archibong, 2014; Nnodim, Agbaenyi & Ugwuegbulem, 2014; Sefridge, 2014; Oguzie, Ani, Obi & Onyegirim, 2018). Problems with which these procedures have been used have ranged from persistent truancy behaviour, conduct disorder, bullying

behaviour and achievement motivation in underachieving students. Since cognitive restructuring and contingency contracting techniques have both been found to be effective in modifying maladaptive behaviours as indicated in relevant literature, the present study was devised to investigate the relative effectiveness of these techniques on bullying behaviour among secondary school students to see if viable changes in students' behaviour could be brought about by guiding counsellors, and teachers in procedures of cognitive restructuring and contingency contracting techniques in order to ensure that the schools have friendlier and safer learning environment. Consequently, this study sought to determine the relative effectiveness of cognitive restructuring and contingency contracting techniques on bullying behaviour of secondary school students in Imo State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to determine the relative effectiveness of Cognitive Restructuring and Contingency Contracting techniques on bullying behaviour of secondary school students in Imo State.

Research Question

The study was guided by the following research question:

1. What is the effectiveness of cognitive restructuring when compared to contingency contracting technique using pretest and posttest mean scores?

Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was stated and tested at the 0.5 level of significance:

1. The effectiveness of cognitive restructuring technique on bullying behaviour of secondary school students when compared to those exposed to contingency contracting technique is not significant as measured by their post test mean scores.

Method

The design for this study was anon-randomized pre-test, post-test quasi-experimental design. According to Nworgu (2006), this is a type of experimental study that determines the effect of treatment paradigm on a non-randomised sample. Quasi experimental research is more so, a research method that is most often used when it is not possible to randomize. In this study, two groups served as treatment group while one group served as a control group. The two groups were tagged experimental groups (E1, E2,) Participants in Experimental Group 1 were treated with cognitive restructuring, those in Group 2 were treated with contingency contracting technique, while those in the control group received conventional counselling technique. All the groups were pre-tested and post-tested. The expanded pre-test post-test design was as described below.

Pre-test-Post-test-Control Design

Grouping	Pre-test	Treatment	Post-test
Experimental (1)	O1	X1	O2
Experimental (2)	O1	X2	O2

key:

C= Control

E1 = Experimental group 1- cognitive restructuring

E2= Experimental group 2- Contingency contracting

O1= Pretest measures

O2 = posttest measures

The study was conducted in Owerri North Local Government Area of Imo State. The population of the study comprised 265 senior secondary (SS11) students that were identified with bullying behaviour in all secondary schools in Owerri North Local Government Area of Imo State managed by Ministry of Education Imo State. The sample size for this study was 91 students. The researcher employed a purposive sampling technique through which three secondary schools with the highest number of students identified with bullying behaviour were selected from the pool of 17 public secondary schools in Owerri North Local Government.

The instrument that was used for this study is a ‘Bullying Behaviour Identification Inventory (BBII) developed by Drew (2005) and re-validated in Nigeria by Odoemelum (2012). The BBII is a 30-item instrument designed to elicit information from students on bullying behaviour as it applies to them were administered. The instrument has two sections: Section “A” contains the bio-data of the respondents while section “B” contains 30 bullying behaviours that are manifested by adolescents. The Inventory (BBII) has statements and phrases indicating bullying behaviour characteristics. The Bullying Behaviour Identification Inventory (BBII) has a test-retest reliability of 0.8 as indicated by Odoemelum (2012). Odoemenam used the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient in computing the instrument. A reliability co-efficient of 0.8 was obtained; hence, the instrument was statistically adjudged to be reliable and considered suitable for research use. The researchers with the help of three trained research assistants distributed copies of the BBII through direct delivery and guided the students on how to respond to them. After the training programme which lasted for eight weeks, the Bullying Behaviour Identification inventory (BBII) was reshuffled and re-administered to the students. The completed copies of the instrument were retrieved and scored. The scores from the second administration of the instrument were referred to as post-test. The data collected for this study were organized in table and analysed. The research question was answered using mean, while the hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance using Analysis of co-variance (ANCOVA).

Results

Table 1: Pretest and Posttest bullying behaviour mean scores of students treated with contingency contracts technique and those treated with cognitive restructuring (Norm = 34.86)

Source of Variation	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Lost Mean	Remark
Cognitive restructuring	30	80.63	64.60	16.03	
Contingency contrasts	27	80.59	63.26	17.33	More effective

Table 1 shows that the students treated with cognitive restructuring technique had pretest mean score of 80.63 and posttest mean score of 64.60 with lost mean 16.03 in their bullying behaviour, while students treated with contingency contracts technique had pretest mean score of 80.59 and

posttest mean score of 63.26 with lost mean 17.33 in their bullying behaviour. With the lost mean of 17.33 greater than 16.03, contingency contracts is slightly more effective than cognitive restructuring in reducing bullying behaviour among secondary school students in Imo state.

Table 2: ANCOVA on the posttest scores of contingency contracts and cognitive restructuring techniques on the bullying behaviour scores of students

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	Cal. F	Pvalue	P ≤ 0.05
Corrected Model	187.1292		93.565			
Intercept	135.324	1	135.324			
Pretest	161.5851		161.585			
Treatment model	24.906	1	24.906	1.417	0.239	NS
Error	948.801	54	17.570			
Total	234352.000	57				
Corrected Total	1135.930	56				

Table 2 indicates that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 56df denominator, the calculated F is 1.417 with Pvalue of 0.239 which is greater than 0.05. Therefore, the third null hypothesis is accepted. So, there is no significant difference in the effectiveness of contingency contracts and cognitive restructuring techniques on the bullying behaviour scores of secondary school students.

Discussion

Findings of the study revealed that the two treatment techniques; Cognitive Restructuring and Contingency Contracting techniques are both effective in reducing bullying behaviour of secondary school students. Findings of the study further revealed that contingency contracting technique was a bit more effective in reducing bullying behaviours of secondary school students in Imo State. The finding agrees with Nnodim, Agbenyi and Ugwuegbulam (2014) whose investigation of the efficacy of contingency contract in the management of bullying behaviour showed the superiority of the technique over the control group in reducing aggression. Similarly, finding of the study equally agreed with Selfridge (2014) whose finding showed that contingency contracting technique was successfully implemented to increased desired behaviour. The results thus suggest that contingency contracts can successfully be implemented to increase a desired behaviour. The reason for this could be attributed to the notion that contingency contracts were written with consideration of social significance and function of behaviour, observation of comparison peers to set goals, and reinforcement for desired behaviours and includes access to reinforcement.

The findings further revealed that the difference in the effectiveness of Cognitive restructuring and Contingency contracting techniques on bullying behaviours of secondary school students is not significant. This shows that both cognitive restructuring and contingency contracting techniques are effective techniques in the reduction of aggressive behaviour among secondary school adolescents. This result has slightly different outcome with that of Adeusi (2013) whose study investigated the efficacy of cognitive restructuring and behavioural Rehearsal

on Conduct Disorder in Adolescents in special correctional centres (Formally called Remand home) in Lagos state, Nigeria. The reason may have to do with the nature of the process involved in the treatment which could be linked to the thought, feelings, beliefs and perception changing process involved in cognitive restructuring. More so, studies have made known that cognitive restructuring has been found to be very effective in the treatment of many forms of antisocial behaviours (Oguzie, Ani, Obi & Onyegirim, 2018).

On the other hand, one important aspect of contingency contracting shown in Mellalieu, Hanton, and O'Brien (2006), is that goals were made specific, difficult (but attainable), and self-generated. This researcher thus believes that these criteria possibly enabled the participant to understand and adhere reliably to the set goal by stating exactly what is expected and ensuring the individual is an active participant during the development of the goal. Consequently, the similarity observed in the relative effectiveness of cognitive restructuring and contingency contracting in treating bullying behaviour, though unforeseen by the researchers, should not be surprising to people.

Conclusions

This study investigated cognitive restructuring and contingency contracting techniques on bullying behaviour of secondary school students in Imo state. Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that both cognitive restructuring and contingency contracting techniques are effective in reducing the bullying behaviours of secondary school students. However, contingency contracting proved to be slightly more effective than cognitive restructuring in the treatment of bullying behaviour among secondary school students in Owerri, Imo State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Contingency technique should be adopted by school counsellors and other allied professionals as an effective treatment techniques in reducing bullying behaviour in the school setting. This will contribute in creating enabling learning environment.
2. School counselors should make sure they make themselves available and also try and get adequate training on the use of counselling skills and techniques which if obtained, will help them improve on their problem solving abilities.

The school management should organize workshop seminar by inviting the Parents Teachers Association (PTA) in order to sensitize them on how to identify bullies and victims at a very early stage. This will help in making proper referral for early treatment. Also, School authorities should forge a link between parents and the community, as well as the private sector in creating awareness about bullying and its negative consequences

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